

Bio-inspired deformable propeller concept for smooth human-UAV interaction and efficient thrust generation

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Abstract—This letter presents a novel deformable propeller concept, 3D-printed in flexible thermoplastic polyurethane, which stores impact energy in the form of elastic energy for smooth collisions, reducing risk in human-UAV interactions. However, such a design experiences elastic deformations when exposed to aerodynamic and centrifugal loads. The most relevant occur in the 3-5 krpm range. At higher speeds, the centrifugal force is dominant and the propeller becomes quite stiff. This work provides an investigation of the propeller deformation angles (which ultimately alter the aerodynamic profile and limit thrust generation) based on Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) simulations. These results are leveraged to introduce two complementary solutions: deformation reduction oriented internal fiber distributions, inspired by the ultra-efficient dragonfly wings (I); anticipatory designs which pre-modify pitch and roll angles based on simulation results to ensure optimal performance at the target rotational velocity (II). This letter offers a multi-configuration analysis, yielding an easy to manufacture propeller with a specific design methodology which results in increased efficiency and reduced impact recovery time. This work presents collision tests with various objects, as well as a proof of concept for its flight capabilities in a conventional quadrotor, including physical interaction with humans. These findings are valuable for the development of collision control strategies for UAVs.

Index Terms: Deformable Propeller, Soft Robotics, Mechanical Design, Aeroelasticity

I. INTRODUCTION

DRONES are attracting a great deal of attention from both academia and industry. Its market potential is enormous [1] due to the benefits they offer to solve tasks typically performed by humans in a cost-effective, safe and efficient way. UAVs have recently been used in different sectors: monitoring, surveillance, inspection, transportation, and entertainment [2]. The main reason of their popularity lies in their compact dimension and the ability to access difficult-to-reach areas.

However, one of the main limitations in the operation of drones is the risk of injury to humans or objects in the environment [3], [4]. In addition, in the event of a collision, the UAV can potentially crash due to damaged propellers. Several ideas have emerged to try to reduce these consequences, both hardware and software. This is the case of safety cages for drones and vision obstacle-avoiding algorithms. Nevertheless, industrial applications demand solutions that allow UAVs to

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Fig. 1. 3D-printed dragonfly-inspired flexible propeller concept for smooth physical interaction with humans, with the ability to absorb impact energy and recover after a collision

physically interact with humans and objects, even in cluttered environments; and strategies to reduce damages produced by unexpected propeller collisions. Within this goal, an innovative approach is the application of soft robotics technologies to the UAV propulsion system, inspired by nature and the way insects fly, as is the case of bio-inspired ornithopters. In the case of multirotors, the combination of soft and rigid components has led to partially flexible propeller designs with a bending node, with the ability to absorb impact energy and recover after a collision. The challenge is to incorporate these deformable characteristics into the propeller without diminishing the efficiency and maneuverability of the vehicle.

This work introduces a novel flexible propeller concept (Figure 1), entirely 3D-printed in thermoplastic polyurethane, and provides an investigation of the propeller deformation angles based on Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) simulations. Propeller deformations are inevitable, but there are ways to limit them. Dragonfly wings are able to improve their efficiency and decrease undesired deformations by optimally distributing the degree of flexibility along their wings, creating a complex and unique internal structure based on veins. This concept has been applied to the proposed design, by altering the internal distribution or infill rate during 3D printing. There is a lower infill rate on the leading edge for impact energy reduction, progressively increasing until reaching a maximum on the trailing edge for greater control of the pitch angle.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II is a review of previous works related to drones safety and deformable propellers, including a discussion of the contributions of this work. This is followed by the design of the flexible propeller in Section III. Section IV introduces the aeroelastic model and the methodology used to perform 2-way Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) simulations, while Section V describes the test bench and the experiments carried out to analyze the

Fig. 2. Illustration of the propeller elastic deformation during rotation. Definition of pitch $\theta(x, \omega)$ and roll $\alpha(x, \omega)$ local deformation angles at a rotational speed ω_P . Definition of local coordinates $X = x/R$ and $Y = y/c(x)$, where R is the blade radius and $c(x)$ is the blade chord.

performance of the propeller. Section VI covers the validation of the methodology and the performance evaluation of several configurations, as well as collision tests with different objects, and a proof of concept of its implementation in a conventional quadrotor. This section ends up with a comparison with existing deformable propellers in the literature. Finally, Section VII exposes the main conclusions of the work.

II. RELATED WORK

Several technologies have recently been introduced to improve the safety of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). Overall, these solutions can be classified into software methodologies for collision avoidance (geometric, force-field, optimized, sense and avoid approaches with different sensors [5]–[7]) and active hardware Collision Impact Reduction solutions, which are within the scope of this work.

Collision impact reduction covers impact energy reduction of the UAV structural assembly (I) and solutions to protect the rotors from collisions (II). The first approach focuses on the introduction of flexible components in the drone, for instance, micro quadcopters with arms that absorb energy in case of impact [8], [9]. This concept has been extended to develop the first UAV entirely 3D-printed in flexible filament [10], which in turn entails mechanical [11] and control challenges [12].

Within the second branch, several solutions have been proposed. The use of protective cages has been widely studied [13]–[16] due to its low cost and simplicity. However, their structure introduces an additional risk of collision, and they greatly affect the performance of the UAV by increasing the weight and, therefore, reducing flight time. As an alternative approach, foldable structures [17], [18] can potentially reduce the risk of crashing, especially when flying through a narrow gap. Another mechanical approach combines rigid guards and soft, deformable mechanisms to reduce crash impact, absorb collision shock and retain resilience [19], [20]. However, such integration may require a complex control strategy and a high resource consumption in practical scenarios.

Finally, in the last few years the concept of a flexible blade [21] has grown in popularity since this structure might enable

blades to deform and recover naturally from a collision, while maintaining enough stiffness to fly. Nevertheless, the partially soft blade designs proposed in the literature remain dangerous for human skin. Furthermore, large blades experience great deformation during rotation, limiting the scalability of the proposed designs. The latest works [22], [23] deal with these problems through a bio-inspired design that combines rigid elements with a flexible bending node that allows deformation of the propeller after impact. These works also investigate and evaluate pitch and roll deformation angles for the first time. Nevertheless, the efficiency with respect to the rigid blade can still be improved, together with the fabrication and scalability issues.

The main contributions of this work are: to develop the first completely flexible propeller design, easy to manufacture, with an efficiency above four-fifths over most of its operating range and a recovery time below 0.3s (I); to investigate the propeller deformation angles using 2-way Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) simulations (II); to provide insight into the effects of variable internal fiber distribution, inspired by dragonfly wings (III); the demonstration that a 3-blade deformable propeller, unlike the rigid case, is more efficient than a 2-blade due to smaller deformable angles, reducing the scalability issue by providing greater thrust for the same diameter (IV); the development of an anticipatory design procedure so that elastic deformations (changes in pitch and roll angles) are pre-modified based on simulation results to ensure optimal performance at the target rotational velocity (V).

III. FLEXIBLE PROPELLER MECHANICAL DESIGN

Unlike previous works, the flexible propeller concept proposed in this work is the first which has been completely 3D-printed in flexible filament (thermoplastic polyurethane). It does not have differentiated rigid and flexible parts, but rather a single flexible component in which the internal density or infill rate of the material is modified during the additive manufacturing process. This allows to obtain different mechanical behaviors of the propeller maintaining the same external structure for an external observer. Therefore, the ease of manufacturing is a clear advantage since it avoids the use of molds and adhesion elements between parts.

Nevertheless, the propeller experiences elastic deformations that alter the local aerodynamic profile of the blade (see Figure 2). In this work, these deflections are modeled through two parameters: pitch $\theta(X, \omega)$ and roll $\alpha(X, \omega)$ local deformation angles, where $X = x/R$ and $Y = y/c(x)$ are the blade local coordinates (R is the blade radius and $c(x)$ is the blade chord). Pitch deformations are defined from the line that connects the leading edge with the trailing edge. For the roll deformations, the line that connects the central axis of the propeller with the midpoint of the line defined for the pitch angle is used. Note that there are other parameters that may be relevant, such as curvature; however, analyzing the complete airfoil in detail is excessively complex both experimentally and in simulation. Also note that in this work it is considered that $\theta(X, 0) = 0$ and $\alpha(X, 0) = 0$; thus considering the elastic deformations with respect to the initial angle.

Fig. 3. Description of the pitch ($\theta(X, 0) = 0$) and roll ($\alpha(X, 0) = 0$) initial deformation angle modification system, based on an easily replaceable PLA shell, whose selection depends on the target rotational speed ω_P (left); Qualitative longitudinal and cross-section dragonfly-inspired infill rate distributions (right)

TABLE I
MANUFACTURING AND POST-MANUFACTURING REQUIREMENTS

Stage	Requirements
Manufacturing	Layer Height $< 0.12mm$
	Print Speed $< 20mm/s$
	Support Structure: Tree
	Bed Temperature $> 50^\circ C$
Post-Manufacturing	Infill overlap $< 30\%$
	Defect Elimination: Acetone
	Calibration precision $< 0.1g$ Assembly

Then, a specific internal fiber distribution is proposed, inspired by the ultra-efficient dragonfly wings (see Figure 3). Specifically, the design has a lower infill rate on the leading edge, progressively increasing until reaching a maximum on the trailing edge. This allows greater control of the pitch angle $\theta(X, \omega)$ and attenuates the decrease in the angle of attack due to the moment generated by the aerodynamic flow when hitting the intrados area close to the trailing edge. It also reduces impact energy in the event of a collision, since collisions commonly occur on the leading edge. The longitudinal infill rate distribution is designed to minimize the upward blade tilt due to lift by increasing the volume of fibers near the blade tip. Centrifugal energy also contributes to dampen $\alpha(X, \omega)$ deformations, especially from 5000 rpm, when the propeller becomes quite stiff, with hardly any new deformations while impact energy increases. The central area of the propeller has a smaller infill rate, imitating the role of the dragonfly wing nodus. Finally, the volume of fibers is also slightly increased close to the blade root as it is a stress concentrator.

The proposed design has been completed with an initial deformation angle modification system (see Figure 3) based on an easily replaceable 3D-printed PLA shell, as an elegant way to improve thrust generation over most of the operating range. The user must select the target rotational speed for the specific mission requirements and, using the simulation results, choose the PLA shell with the corresponding $\theta(X, 0)$ and $\alpha(X, 0)$ angles. Table II proposes multiple quantitative configurations ($A_1 = 3, A_2 = -3, A_3 = 1.5, B_1 = 1.5, B_2 = 0.1, B_3 = 0.5$)

Fig. 4. Deformable propeller mechanical design process: infill rate distribution design (a), manufacturing and post-manufacturing (b), characterization and validation of the propeller (deformation angles, thrust efficiency, recovery time) for a range of rotational speeds (c). Then, the user selects ω_P for the specific mission requirements and, using the propeller characterization, chooses the PLA shell with the proper $\theta(X, 0)$ and $\alpha(X, 0)$ angles.

TABLE II
SET OF INFILL RATE DISTRIBUTIONS AND INITIAL DEFORMATION ANGLES CONFIGURATIONS PROPOSED FOR INVESTIGATION

	Infill Rate Distribution $\rho(X, Y)$	$\theta_{\omega=0}$	$\alpha_{\omega=0}$
C1	ρ_0	0	0
C2	$\rho_0(A_1 X^2 + A_2 X + A_3)$	0	0
C3	$\rho_0(B_1 Y^2 + B_2 Y + B_3)$	0	0
C4	$\rho_0(A_1 X^2 + A_2 X + A_3)(B_1 Y^2 + B_2 Y + B_3)$	0	0
C5	$\rho_0(A_1 X^2 + A_2 X + A_3)(B_1 Y^2 + B_2 Y + B_3)$	0	$-\alpha_{\omega_P}$
C6	$\rho_0(A_1 X^2 + A_2 X + A_3)(B_1 Y^2 + B_2 Y + B_3)$	$-\theta_{\omega_P}$	0
C7	$\rho_0(A_1 X^2 + A_2 X + A_3)(B_1 Y^2 + B_2 Y + B_3)$	$-\theta_{\omega_P}$	$-\alpha_{\omega_P}$

for the infill rate distribution (inspired by dragonfly wings, since an analytical optimization process is outside the scope of this article) and initial deformable angles, in order to provide insight into the influence of these solutions.

The stages shown in green in the procedure also play a critical role in the propeller performance (see Table I). 3D printing speed must be low to avoid oscillations during the process due to the shape of the blade ($< 20mm/s$), while layer height must be smaller than 0.12 mm to ensure correct adhesion between fiber layers. Other requirements to take into account are a tree-type support, a bed temperature greater than 50 degrees to ensure good adhesion and an infill overlap below 30% so that the leading and trailing edges remain deformable in the event of an impact. Post manufacturing includes the defect removal process using acetone and blade calibration. This calibration is intended to accurately match the weight of the blades, as these deviations are the main source of oscillations in operation. Sustained oscillations have been found (with an impact greater than 10% on propeller efficiency) for deviations greater than 0.1g.

IV. MECHANICAL MODELING OF THE PROPELLER

A. Non-linear elastic problem

In the design of deformable propellers, previous works propose simplified material resistance models to approximately

Fig. 5. Iterative process for the 2-way Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) simulations. Aerodynamic and elastic problems are coupled since propeller deformation modifies the geometry and therefore pressure distribution.

calculate deformations. However, in this work the flexibility is not restricted to a single bending node but to the entire propeller. This, together with the complexity of the geometry and the distribution of forces, require to switch to non-linear elasticity theory.

A hyperelastic material is a type of constitutive model where the non-linear stress-strain relationship derives from a strain energy density function W . In this work, the energetic approach is closed using the 5-parameter Mooney-Rivlin non-linear model (1), typically used to model the elastic response of rubber-like materials. In this model, I_1 and I_2 are the invariants of the left Cauchy-Green deformation tensor B_{ij} , which is defined as (2), where u_i are the displacements and X_k the initial position.

$$W = \sum_{i,j=0}^{N=2} C_{ij}(I_1 - 3)^i(I_2 - 3)^j \quad (1)$$

$$B_{ij} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial X_K} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial X_K} \quad (2)$$

These Mooney-Rivlin parameters C_{ij} for TPU have been obtained experimentally in previous works developed by the authors [11] and are shown for some infill rates in Table III. Note that infill rate variations translate into changes in C_{ij} , which should be considered for modeling in simulation the internal fiber distributions proposed in this work.

Once the strain energy density function has been characterized, the stress-strain relationship can be obtained from the Piola-Kirchhoff equations that are included in the Ansys Mechanics commercial software. This software also includes Cauchy's equilibrium equations for stress σ_{ij} required to model the boundary conditions X_i (rotation torque ω_P and aerodynamic pressure distribution for the propeller) and Saint-Venant's compatibility equations for the $\epsilon_{ij} - u_i$ relationship. All these equations are solved using the finite element method.

B. Aerodynamic analysis

The commercial software Ansys Fluent has been used to solve the aerodynamic problem. The governing Navier-Stokes equations of fluid mechanics are based on the conservation of mass (3) and momentum (4), since energy is not considered in this work. The flow around a propeller can be considered

TABLE III
EXPERIMENTALLY-MEASURED MOONEY-RIVLIN COEFFICIENTS FOR TPU AND DIFFERENT INTERNAL DENSITIES ρ_{TPU}

$\rho_{TPU}(\%)$	$C10$	$C01$	$C20$	$C02$	$C11$
6	-3.19	4.23	0.64	-2.65	4.37
8	-4.07	4.18	0.71	-2.62	4.54
10	-4.51	4.16	0.76	-2.75	4.89

incompressible ($M < 0.3$), so these equations have been simplified.

$$\nabla \vec{v} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + \rho(\vec{v} \nabla \vec{v}) = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \vec{v} + \rho g \quad (4)$$

In equations (3,4), p is the static pressure, ρ is the density, \vec{v} is the flow velocity, ρg are the gravitational forces, and μ is the viscosity. These equations are decomposed into mean and fluctuating parts, leading to the Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) equations. The resulting equations are not developed in detail for simplicity. However, note that the Reynolds stress tensor ($-\rho \overline{v'_i v'_j}$) requires a turbulent model to close the system of equations. In this work, a $k-\epsilon$ turbulent model with standard wall functions is proposed. This model is especially suitable for flows where rotation plays a fundamental role. Finally, the flow around the propeller is studied using the Multiple Reference Frame (MRF) method [24].

C. 2-way Fluid-Structure Interaction Simulations

Aeroelasticity comprises the study of the interactions between elastic and aerodynamic forces occurring while an elastic body (e.g. a deformable propeller) is exposed to a fluid flow. A first and popular approach, is to carry out these simulations performing the aerodynamic analysis considering a rigid body, and using the output pressure field as external force and input of the elastic problem. Although this solution can provide approximate results in many problems, it is not enough in the present case since the relative deformations of the propeller are not small.

When the relative deformations are greater than 10%, the pressure field obtained from the aerodynamic analysis carried out on the body approximated as rigid is no longer valid in the deformed configuration of the elastic body. Moreover, this new pressure field will modify the elastic forces and lead to a new deformed configuration. In other words, the elastic and aerodynamic problems are coupled, and the problem must be solved by an iterative method that progressively increases the load. This is the 2-way Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) simulations concept shown in Figure 5.

D. Flexible Propeller Efficiency and Recovery Time

In this work, the efficiency of the deformable propeller η_P is defined as the thrust provided T_{flex} in comparison to a propeller with rigid blades T_{rigid} (5). These thrust losses are caused by the deformations of the flexible propeller, which modify the aerodynamic profile of the blades.

$$\eta_P = \frac{T_{flex}}{T_{rigid}} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 6. Experimental setup: UAV prototype equipped with flexible propellers (Right); test bench prototype (Middle); CAD design and description of the experiments: thrust measurement, deformable angles, collision tests (Left)

In the event of a collision, the propeller stores impact energy in the form of elastic energy. However, this deformation process entails transient thrust losses which are characterized by η_T (6) during the collision time t_c (in which N_c collisions occur). The recovery time t_r is defined as the time elapsed between the last collision and the instant in which the nominal thrust is recovered at the rotational speed of the propeller.

$$\eta_T = \frac{T_c}{T_{flex}} \quad (6)$$

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental analysis of the propeller performance (thrust analysis, deformation angles and recovery time) has been carried out in the bench test described in Figure 6, as well as in flight on a quadrotor. These experiments are used to validate the aeroelastic simulations presented in the previous section, and to perform collision and recovery tests with objects.

Test bench includes the unidirectional load cell from TE Connectivity for thrust measurement, the DJI 2312E motor, and the DJI 430 Lite ESC. For the exact measurement of the propeller rotational speeds, a digital tachometer from RS Spain has been used.

For the deformable angles measurement, a Sony high-speed camera at 1000 fps has been used. To obtain $\alpha(X, \omega_P)$, the camera has been placed in the position shown in Figure 6, allowing the measurement of the vertical displacement of the blade, which in turn leads to the roll angle using basic trigonometry. To obtain $\theta(X, \omega_P)$ the blade chord has been measured in Experiment 3. The relationship between chord and pitch angle can be obtained by post-processing in Matlab as the exact geometry of the blade is known.

The fourth experiment consists of propeller impact analysis and recovery time measurement. For this, two kind of objects have been studied: carbon fiber rods, and human fingers. Impact tests have been carried out along different points of the propeller ($X = x/R$).

Finally, a quadrotor platform (Figure 6, right) has been designed to carry out flight tests with the deformable propellers and analyze the physical interaction process with humans. The proposed UAV is a conventional quadrotor weighing 1.4 kg, including 4S batteries, the Ardupilot commercial autopilot installed in a CUAV V5, an X8R receiver and the DJI motors and ESCs used in the test bench.

Fig. 7. Experimental results (solid lines with error bars) and simulation results (circles) for rigid and flexible propeller (Configuration 1) thrust measurements (black) and flexible propeller deformation angles (green), for different rotational speeds (rpm)

VI. RESULTS

A. Methodology validation

This section provides a comparison between simulation results obtained through the methodology described in section IV, and the experimental results carried out in the bench test presented in section V. To do this, thrust values are shown in Figure 7 (for the flexible and the rigid propeller) together with pitch θ and roll α deformation angles (at $X = 0.75$), for different rotational speeds of the propeller (rpm). The flexible propeller considered in this case corresponds to Configuration 1 with an infill rate of 30%.

The experimental results include error bars that model the error of the measuring instruments: the force sensor in the case of thrust; and the quality of the images at high rotational speeds, in the case of deformation angles. Simulation-experimental discrepancies are within experimental uncertainties (errors below 10%).

The results show that both roll α and pitch angle θ follow a slightly quadratic evolution. From 5000 rpm, the propeller becomes quite rigid due to the centrifugal force and the deflection angles stabilize. However, that range is not interesting since impact energy also increases considerably, so Figure 7 focuses on the 3-5 krpm range. Another noteworthy point from Figure 7 is that discrepancies increase at high rotational speeds. The reason is related to the vibrations that the propeller experiences due to small errors during the calibration process.

B. Number of blades

For rigid blades, it is known that increasing the number of blades reduces efficiency, since the aerodynamic drag of the additional blades make the L/D ratio lower. However, 2-blade propellers require a significantly larger diameter for the same amount of thrust. In the flexible case, this leads to greater deformations and, therefore, greater efficiency losses. This work shows that the triple blade configuration is 5% more efficient in a deformable propeller (for the same configuration and infill rate).

The increased efficiency is not the only advantage of increasing the number of blades. A 2-blade propeller produces two pressure pulses per revolution, whereas a 3-blade propeller will produce three smaller pulses per revolution for the same amount of total thrust. As a result, the 3-blade prop will be inherently smoother and therefore quieter. Lastly, recovery in

Fig. 8. Normalized local thrust along the propeller blade span ($X = x/R$) for the rigid and flexible propellers. Evolution of pitch and roll deformation angles along the blade span.

the event of a collision is easier and faster since 2 propellers are kept in operation while the third one impacts.

C. Multiple configurations comparison

Table II described the different configurations that are compared in this section. In each of them, the longitudinal infill rate distribution, the cross-sectional distribution, or both, are modified. Configurations 5-7 also include the initial deformation angle modification system. The comparison is made in terms of thrust efficiency (η_P) and deformation angles.

Note that deformation angles are local variables that vary over the span of the blade ($\theta(X, \omega_P)$, $\alpha(X, \omega_P)$). For this reason, the spatial distribution of these angles for Configuration 1 is shown in Figure 8. Obviously these angles increase (approximately following a quadratic shape) from the root to the blade tip. It is also interesting to observe the local evolution of the thrust generated along the blade. In the rigid case, there is a clear maximum around $X = 0.8$, although in the flexible case, the curve is more distributed, with most of the thrust being generated between $X = 0.5$ and $X = 0.9$.

These results justify the choice of $\theta_{\omega=0} = -\theta_{\omega_P}(X = 0.75)$ and $\alpha_{\omega=0} = -\alpha_{\omega_P}(X = 0.75)$ as the pitch and roll initial deformation angles of the flexible propeller (at the target rotation speed) for the design of the PLA shell. In this way, the angles will be close to their optimum, in the vicinity of $X = 0.75$, where most of the thrust is generated.

Figure 9 shows the evolution of propeller efficiency and deformation angles for Configurations 1-7. Configurations 2 and 3 aim to show the influence of longitudinal and cross-section infill rate distributions independently. In Configuration 2 (variable longitudinal infill rate) roll deformations are reduced by approximately 28%. Meanwhile, in Configuration 3 (variable infill rate cross-section) pitch deformations are reduced by 33%. In configuration 4, the improvement is 31% and 34%, respectively. The influence of the dragonfly-inspired infill rate distribution (Configuration 4) is of the order of 8% on thrust efficiency.

Finally, the system for modifying the initial deformation angles is added to Configuration 4. These are chosen to optimize performance at a target rotational speed of 4000 rpm, corresponding to $\theta_{\omega=0} = -11.8$ and $\alpha_{\omega=0} = -9.7$. Configurations 5 and 6 show thrust improvements of 5.5 and 4.4%, respectively. Finally, Configuration 7 reaches up to

Fig. 9. Thrust efficiency η_P (black) as a function of rotational speed for Configurations 1-7. Roll (green solid lines) and pitch (green dashed lines) deformation angles are also showcased. The graphical interpretation of the premodified angles for the target rotational speed is also shown.

TABLE IV
EFFICIENCY COMPARISON FOR DIFFERENT AVERAGE INFILL RATE (CONFIGURATION 7) BETWEEN 3000 AND 4000 RPM

Average Infill Rate	Efficiency
10%	62 – 73%
25%	79 – 85%
50%	82 – 87%

$\eta_P = 0.86$ at the target rotational speed. Note that, despite the fact that the pitch and roll angles are almost optimal (corresponding to the rigid case) at $X = 0.75$, they are not for the rest of the blade span, hence the remaining discrepancies. In addition, as indicated at the beginning of this article, these two angles are not the only parameters that define the geometry of the propeller, for instance consider the curvature.

Finally, it is convenient to analyze the influence of the average infill rate of the deformable propeller (Table IV). At low average infill rates (10%, high flexibilities) efficiency drops rapidly to around 62-73%. On the other hand, at high average infill rates, the increased stiffness leads to higher efficiency while it may become more dangerous in the event of a collision with objects such as human skin. For this reason, an equilibrium solution would be an average infill rate around 25 - 30%.

D. Collision Tests and Recovery Time

As shown in Figure 10, during a collision several stages occur: first, pitch angle increases after impact (I); subsequently, the stored impact energy is converted by the propeller to elastic energy, specifically, increasing the roll angle, reducing impact force with the object (II); next, these blade elastic deformations are transmitted to the rest of the blades, leading to minimum thrust values since all the blades are strongly deformed (III); finally, the propeller recovers after around 0.3s providing the nominal thrust again (IV).

In addition, Figure 11 shows the temporal evolution of thrust during several collision tests. These tests have been carried out with consecutive impacts N_c , for the configurations shown in Table V. It is observed that, during collision time t_c , thrust remains practically constant, as long as the object is placed at the same impact point during the process. Thrust losses vary from barely 30% in the human finger case, up to nearly 70% in the carbon fiber case at $X = 0.8$. It is also observed that, in accordance with the images shown in Figure 10, recovery times t_r are smaller in the human finger case (just 0.2s).

Fig. 10. Impact and recovery tests for a carbon fiber stick (upper images) and a human finger (lower images). Each image corresponds to a different stage of the multi-step collision process.

E. Flight Tests

Flight experiments have been carried out with the quadrotor described in section V. In these experiments, the quadrotor has been positioned close to a human person to perform physical interaction as proof of concept of the risk reduction that a flexible propeller supposes (see Figure 12). During these flight experiments, the stability of the quadrotor has been verified, demonstrating that the influence of inertial forces is practically negligible compared to aerodynamic and centrifugal forces.

F. Literature comparison

The proposed flexible propeller concept, 3D-printed in thermoplastic polyurethane (for Configuration 7 with a 25% average infill rate) has been compared (Table VI) with the designs presented in the literature [21], [22].

The design presented in [21] offers the highest efficiency, due to the hardness of PET (around 60D on the Shore Hardness scale). However, it hardly stores elastic energy during impact, remaining dangerous to human skin and leading to relatively high recovery times.

On the other hand, in [22] the elastic energy stored during impact is increased by including a silicone node, while the rest of the propeller is made of rigid plastic. This allows to reduce the recovery time to 0.4s. However, deformations appear in the propeller, which are difficult to model given the unpredictability of silicone. In addition, the manufacturing process is complex, including the use of molds. Nevertheless,

Fig. 11. Temporal evolution of thrust during deformable propeller (Configuration 7 at 3500 rpm) collisions with a $D=5\text{mm}$ carbon fiber rod (left) and a $D=10\text{mm}$ human finger (right) at points $X = 0.8$ (upper) and $X = 0.9$ (lower). Experimental evaluation of collision time (t_c), number of collisions (N_c), recovery time (t_r) and thrust efficiency during collisions (η_T).

TABLE V
COLLISION TESTS RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT OBJECTS AND IMPACT POINTS

	Impact	t_c	N_c	t_r	η_T
Carbon $D = 5\text{mm}$	$X = 0.8$	2.3s	400	0.32s	34%
Carbon $D = 5\text{mm}$	$X = 0.9$	1.4s	250	0.36s	56%
Human Finger $D = 10\text{mm}$	$X = 0.8$	1.7s	300	0.31s	58%
Human Finger $D = 10\text{mm}$	$X = 0.9$	1.9s	340	0.21s	71%

this design can be more robust against collisions and achieve higher repeatability between prototypes.

Finally, in this work the propeller is 3D-printed entirely in flexible TPU filament (hardness D scale between 20-30 and A scale between 70-90, the lowest of all those presented). Propeller deformations have been modeled and solutions to control them have been presented, reaching efficiencies up to 86%. Recovery times are low and the propeller stores a large amount of elastic energy during impact, demonstrating its use for physical interaction with humans. Manufacturing is fast and simple, although its scalability is limited by the large deformations that appear as the diameter increases. The difficulty of maintaining a high repeatability between prototypes is another disadvantage.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

A novel deformable propeller concept, 3D-printed in flexible thermoplastic polyurethane, which stores impact energy in the form of elastic energy for smooth collisions, has been presented. This approach is specially suitable for drone applications, reducing risk in human-UAV interactions.

This work has provided an investigation of the propeller deformation angles based on Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) simulations, which ultimately alter the aerodynamic profile and limit thrust generation.

This work has proposed two complementary solutions to deal with these undesired deformations. First, the modification of the propeller infill rate distribution, imitating ultra-efficient dragonfly wings. Specifically, the results show that a lower infill rate on the leading edge for impact energy reduction, progressively increasing until reaching a maximum on the trailing edge, can reduce pitch angle deformations by 31%.

Fig. 12. Flexible propeller flight capability proof of concept in a conventional quadrotor. Demonstration of reduced risk in physical interaction with humans.

TABLE VI

COMPARISON OF DEFORMABLE PROPELLERS FROM THE LITERATURE

Propeller	η	t_r	Scalability	Fabrication	Material
J. Jang [21]	> 95%	$\approx 1s$	< 20kg UAV	3D-printing	PET
Tombo [22]	77.4%	0.4s	< 10kg UAV	Molds	PLA + Silicone
Present	78 – 86%	< 0.3s	< 10kg UAV	3D-printing	TPU

Similarly, the longitudinal infill rate distribution is designed to minimize the upward blade tilt (up to 34%) due to lift by increasing the volume of fibers near the blade tip. These solutions increase propeller efficiency by 8%.

On the other hand, it is proposed to modify the initial (at zero rotational speed) pitch and roll angles (anticipatory design). This is achieved using an easily replaceable PLA shell, which optimizes the performance of the propeller for the target rotational speed, and can be quickly substituted depending on mission requirements. These angles are selected considering the propeller blade thrust generation span distribution. With this system, efficiencies of up to 86 % have been achieved while the propeller remains close to the target rotational speed.

Finally, this work also provides collision tests with different objects, analyzing thrust loss during the collisions (between 30 and 70 % depending on the material properties) demonstrating recovery times below 0.3s; as well as a proof of concept of its flight capability in a conventional quadrotor including physical interaction with humans.

Nevertheless, in this easy to manufacture propeller the increased flexibility limits the scalability of the design to bigger diameter blades, since large, hard to control deformations would occur. The use of the proposed deformable propeller concept is restricted to UAVs weighing less than 10kg.

This work does not cover the development of specific collision-accommodated control for UAVs considering thrust variations experienced by the deformed propeller during the collision process, which will be presented in future work.

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